

A survey on Priority Based Job Scheduling in Cloud Computing

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Abstract- The increasing demand for cloud computing demonstrates how resources are being controlled with the need to schedule every incoming jobs. Cloud computing faces numerous challenges, with job scheduling being a particularly complex issue and scheduling belongs to category of NP-hard problems. From this viewpoint, numerous strategies are used to schedule incoming job requests in accordance with the needs of cloud users. Users can scale up and down resources from distant locations by using the cloud on a pay-per-use basis. As demand increases, it becomes increasingly important to efficiently manage resources by considering priority and non-priority based approaches. The effectiveness of various priority and non priority based job scheduling techniques is the main focus of this study with the goal to examine and evaluate the issues associated with distributing jobs across limited cloud-based resources.

Keywords: Cloud computing, job scheduling, priority

I. INTRODUCTION

The term cloud computing refers to a technique of providing resources online to users as and when needed. These resources are available in data centers owned by cloud service providers. The resources are requested by the cloud user, and they mention the need for resources in each request. When any of the request is made, the cloud service provider creates a queue of all requests, schedules them on the server (a physical computer), and then allocates resources to them. Cloud customers use resources in accordance with their demands, and cloud providers make these resources available to cloud consumers upon request and charge them according to the time and amount of usage. For this a broker is designed to explore potential strategies for distributing a set of easily accessible limited resources to new users in order to optimize scheduling objectives such as makespan, computational cost, financial cost,

reliability, availability, resource utilization, response time, energy consumption, and more[1], [2].

Before offering cloud services to customers, a service level agreement (SLA) is finalized, guaranteeing the quality of service (QoS) that both parties agree upon. This enables cloud users to focus on their intended tasks rather than on the resources being used. Numerous corporate enterprises can dynamically scale up their resource requirements using cloud computing on-demand approaches without significant hardware and software investments. Numerous scientific fields, such as data mining, business informatics, physics, astronomy and bioinformatics, rely on applications that demand substantial computational power to complete jobs within reasonable time frames[3]. In recent years, the escalating computational needs of users have led to the deployment of large-scale applications on cloud platforms. This shift leverages the cloud's inherent flexibility and elasticity, enabling consumers to

access resources as needed through a pay-per-use model.

The need of cloud computing is growing day by day because of its versatility, scalability and remarkable affordability. The processing of substantial data volumes can result in diminished performance when job scheduling is not optimized effectively. Job scheduling plays a crucial role in resource management (RR) by determining the execution order and allocation of jobs within a system. This process involves the precise assignment of resource components and the establishment of completion timeliness for each job.

In cloud computing, scheduling is employed to enhance performance and maximize system throughput. The effectiveness, speed and optimal use of resources are largely determined by the chosen scheduling method for the cloud environment. Various criteria are considered in scheduling ensuring the fulfillment of comprehensive user Quality of Service(QoS) performance such as maximizing CPU usage, minimizing makespan, reducing turnaround time, decreasing waiting time ,lowering response time and more[4]. The development of efficient scheduling algorithms has been a primary focus for numerous researchers, aiming to discover swift and effective answers to the job scheduling challenges prevalent in cloud computing environments.

Motivation to Conduct the Research

To meet the objectives of both cloud service providers and their users, resource scheduling handles a large volume of user demands and allocates them to the most suitable machines. To optimize the use of virtual machines and reduce the operational costs of data centers, effective resource scheduling is essential. This approach enhances the quality of service (QoS) metrics in cloud computing. We draw inspiration from concepts found in peer surveys within previous literary works. A variety of research has been carried out to examine job scheduling methods in cloud environments[1], [2], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12] which are summarized in table 1. Moreover, some of the current surveys is comprehensive, and some addresses all the QoS characteristics simultaneously. But none of the existing survey focused on priority

based job scheduling algorithm in cloud computing. This works present a survey on various priority based job scheduling in cloud computing. To conclude, the main contributions of this paper are outlined as follows:

Section 1: Introduction of cloud computing

Section 2: Related work in the field of cloud computing.

Section 3: Overview of scheduling objectives

Section 4: Focuses on Priority based job scheduling in cloud computing

Section 5: Conclusion

Table 1: An overview of related survey and review article along with comprehensive survey and review articles

References	Review type	Idea	Publication year	Review mechanism	Our review
[1]	Review	Comprehensively reviewed task scheduling techniques	2021	Task scheduling	Focus on meta-heuristics scheduling algorithm
[2]	Survey	Comprehensively reviewed cloud computing scheduling techniques	2023	Task scheduling	Focus on Nature insp optimization algorithm
[5]	Review	Comprehensively reviewed cloud dynamic load balancing and reactive fault tolerance technique	2022	Load balancing and fault tolerance techniques	Focus on load balancing reactive fault toler techniques
[6]	Survey	PSO based meta-heuristic scheduling technique in cloud	2022	Particle swarm optimization techniques	Emphasis on broad domain diverse model of PSO
[7]	Review	Comprehensively reviewed Workflow scheduling in cloud	2022	Workflow scheduling framework	Focus on various challenges issue in workflow schedu approaches
[8]	Review	Scientific workflow scheduling and management in cloud	2023	Scientific workflow	Concentrate on different mo
[9]	Review	Described current research on task scheduling and VM consolidation	2023	Energy efficiency	Focus on different schedu methods and consolidi schemes
[10]	Review	Review and proposed priority-based scheduling technique	2022	Job scheduling	Review on job schedu techniques
[11]	Survey	Comprehensive survey of task scheduling strategy based on method, application and parameter	2019	Task scheduling	Focus on issue of schedu methodologies
[12]	Review	Systematic reviewed priority based scheduling algorithm	2013	Job scheduling	Review and compare var priority based job schedu techniques

II. RELATED WORK

In recent times, numerous survey and literature review have been undertaken to examine resource allocation and job scheduling within cloud computing environment. This study analyzed resource allocation and focused on different job

scheduling strategies or algorithms used in cloud computing.

Resource allocation

[13] Proposed a Generalized Knapsack Algorithm as a novel approach for allocation of cloud resource by maximizing resource utilization while considering various constraints. This algorithm has exhibited notable advantages in terms of performance and ability to handle increasing workload.

In review paper [14] author provide a thorough review for hybrid scheduling algorithm utilized in cloud computing. The algorithm combines multiple techniques to optimize resource allocation, aiming to improve utilization, reduce energy consumption, minimize makespan, balance workload and enhance QoS. The author classify hybrid algorithm into four categories: meta-heuristic, nature-inspired, machine learning-based and multi-objective optimization methods.

The work in [15] proposed HCCG algorithm which aims to provide optimize resource utilization by maximize compaction while taking into account various limitation including processing power, network capacities and storage capacity of available resources. The author of [16]proposed MQS algorithm that employs a global scheduler strategy to enhance cloud resource efficiency and minimizes expenses for both reservation and on-demand plans.

Job Scheduling

Cloud computing environment typically utilize three primary categories of job scheduling algorithms[17]: Conventional Scheduling methods including first-come first-serve(FCFS), shortest job first (SJF), largest job first(LJF) and round robin(RR).

Approximation techniques such as Min-min and Max-min algorithms.

Advanced optimization strategies like ant colony optimization (ACO) and particle swarm optimization (PSO).

III. OVERVIEW OF JOB SCHEDULING OBJECTIVES

In cloud computing the main goals of scheduling involve several crucial elements, each essential for

enhancing performance and making the use of most of the resources as illustrated in table 2.

Nature of scheduling problem

Designing an optimization model that successfully fulfills the objectives by determining the best possible solution is vital due to the inherent balance between optimization goals. Therefore two categories of scheduling objectives are taken into account for job scheduling based on priority.

Single objective function

Single objective optimization problems concentrate on enhancing a single goal, typically resulting in a straight forward and definitive solution. In single objective optimization; it is possible to assess how optimal a particular solution is compared to an existing one. For previously defined objectives, an appropriate solution is selected. In cloud computing job scheduling; the majority of methods mainly focus on the demands for CPU and memory requirements. Here are presenting some of the research based on single objective function. In [18] an algorithm is introduced to prioritized and processed preempted task in waiting queue. This strategy reduced the execution time of preempted task. In the research [19] a parallel genetic algorithm (GA) utilizing a Map Reduce framework was introduced for job scheduling in cloud computing environment with varying priority queues. The main objective is to minimize the overall execution time of the task scheduling process through the use of Map Reduce framework. In the research work[20] a Discrete Prey-Predator model for cloud task scheduling, designed to optimize the process by assigning survival values to various scheduling solutions, thereby enhancing decision making in task allocation. The study also conducted a simulation showing that the Discrete Prey-Predator model surpasses the firefly algorithm in reducing execution times for cloud job scheduling.

Multi objective function

Multi-objective function means trying to improve several goals at the same time, even when they conflict. This is harder than focusing on just one goal because you have to find a balance between the different goals[21], [22].In multi objective function, directly comparing the optimality of one solution to

another is not feasible. Instead, multi objective scheduling frequently employs a Pareto dominance relation method, which substitutes a single optimal solution with arrange of options, offering numerous and diverse trade-offs among the objectives. Job scheduling within a distributed heterogeneous computing system is characterized as a non-linear, multi objective and NP-hard optimization problem. The primary objective is to optimize cloud resource utilization while ensuring adherence to Quality of Service (QoS) standards[23].

IV. CLASSIFICATION OF JOB SCHEDULING OBJECTIVES

The minimum of one objective function must be present throughout the job scheduling process in order to get optimal efficiency. The scheduling process assigns job in the workflow to the right resources based on predetermined scheduling criteria. The summary of objective function of job scheduling is listed in table 2

Makespan

It refers to the overall duration required to finish executing a series of tasks or jobs within a computing system.[2], [3].Reducing it is a frequent objective in scheduling algorithms because it significantly affects the system’s efficiency and performance. It also refers to the time span from the start of the first task or job to the end of the last one in a scheduling context[24].In the existing literature, a significant algorithms have primarily aimed at optimizing makespan. However, by focusing on reducing the total execution time, it is possible to decrease execution costs while effectively mapping tasks to resources[25], [26].

Resource utilization

By leasing limited resources to users, the service provider enhances resource utilization, thereby increasing profits by ensuring that these resources are fully utilized. Moreover, there is an invincible relationship between resource and energy use[27].This signifies that resources having low utilization rates continue to use excessive amount of energy in contrast to resources that are completely utilized or correctly loaded in cloud computing.

Waiting Time

Waiting time refers to how long a process waits before the allocation of resource. All cloudlets must wait in the main queue before they assigned any resources.

Flow time

Flow time encompasses the entire duration needed to transition from one operation to the next. This includes any waiting period for the machines or work orders to become available, any downtime caused by machine malfunctions, and any delays due to process interruptions or shortages of components.

Execution time

It refers to the duration required for a job to finish a task. The scheduling of a job is influenced by the work environment and the desired outcomes.

Throughput

The amount of work gets completed in per unit of time.

Execution cost

Optimizing costs is a crucial concern in cloud computing. In terms of infrastructure, the goals of cloud service providers (CSPs) often conflict with those of end users. Amazon EC2 services offer several pricing models, including on-demand resources, advanced reservations, and spot instances.

Table 2: Objective function of job scheduling

Ref.	Scheduling algorithm	Makespan time	Waiting Time	Flow Time	Response time	Execution time	Resource Utilization	Execution Cost	Starvation	Throughput
[28]	PBFS	v	v	v						
[29]	CJS	v	v				v			
[30]	RASA	v								
[31]	PSO	v								
[32]	A2DJS	v					v		v	
[33]	GATS+	v					v			
[34]	Greedy based	v								
[35]	Improved cost based	v						v		
[36]	IASOA	v								v
[37]	QHS		v		v					
[38]	GA-WOA				v		v			v
[39]		v					v			v
[40]	Scheduling	v	v				v			
[41]	Deadline Aware	v				v				
[42]	Dynamic priority based on cost					v		v		
[43]	CSA-MSA	v						v		v
[18]	EDF					v				
[44]	SGPBFS	v		v						
[20]	Discrete Prey-Predator					v				
[19]	GA					v				
[45]	BWO	v	v			v	v			
[46]	GA-GWO	v						v		

V. A Priority-Based Job Scheduling Algorithm in Cloud Computing

Various priority-based job-scheduling algorithms for cloud computing have been developed. A priority assignment algorithm [47] was introduced based on a new data structure, known as waiting time matrix, for assigning priority to each task. The task with the higher priority is extracted from the waiting queue by adhering to the principle of Fibonacci heap. In [48] proposed a scheduling algorithm for decision-making using multi-criteria. In [49] a new multi-criteria priority-aware job scheduling algorithm for cloud computing was presented. Another [50] priority based algorithm was introduced using an iterative method. The PBFS algorithm [28] optimizes job scheduling by allocating resources at the most efficient times. This method was created by considering three essential factors: CPU time, arrival time, and job duration. To enhance cloud job scheduling, a specific backfilling approach known as Earliest Gap Shortest Job First (EG-SJF) was developed. This technique focuses on filling schedule gaps in a particular sequence to improve overall efficiency.

Murad et.al. have introduced a novel cloud job scheduling called SG-PBFS [44] to address the complexities of dynamic cloud environments. This method integrates the prioritization of jobs using PBFS with the placement of these jobs into the smallest available gaps through the Shortest Gap strategy. Although simulations indicate that SG-PBFS surpasses existing algorithms in terms of completion time and tardiness, the study fails to explore how it manages job interruptions for higher priority tasks i.e., preemption. Furthermore, conducting tests in real-world scenarios would enhance the understanding of SG-PBFS's efficacy in cloud environments.

In [51] fair-priority scheduling concept was introduced that is a combination of priority with a round-robin scheduling scheme. This brings fairness to priority level and increases the utilization of resources at the system level. The researchers categorized all tasks into two main groups: those with deadline based constraints and those with minimum cost based constraints. Following dynamic optimization, fairness was prioritized. The system

implements three priority levels (high, medium and low) using a round robin approach, with each level assign specific weights.

A novel approach, known as MCPTS [52] was implemented to address priority concerns in both user requests and provider resources. This efficient priority task scheduling system adjusts priorities based on four key task parameters: length, waiting time, deadline, and burst time. The MCPTS framework is composed of three sub-models: task priority, task queuing priority and resource priority. To assess and establish task priorities, researchers proposed a new hybrid multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) method that combines ELECTRE III with a meta-heuristic algorithm called differential evolution.

A more effective Backfill Algorithm can maximize resource utilization by employing a multilevel queue system [53]. This approach organizes processes with identical priorities into separate queues, following a First-Come-First-Served (FCFS) order, and creates N queues for N priority levels. The resulting consolidated queue is then processed by the EASY backfill component, adhering to the priority sequence. By combining the Enhanced Backfill Algorithm with the EASY algorithm, this method achieves priority-based resource optimization.

In [54] the author considered both the cost and priority of the task assigned by the user to minimize the makespan.

In the work [55] suggested a scheduling method at task level that assign priorities to task whereas [10] proposed an algorithm based on two considerations. All jobs are sorted into two categories based on priority parameters and non-priority. In [56] a new processor scheduling approach based on the KNAPSACK algorithm was introduced that address the issue of waiting states and starvation faced by low-priority processes. This method aims to eliminate these problems in process management.

[57] proposed technique uses a neural network to classify the job queues that exist on any resource and to different jobs. While in [58] the author suggests an algorithm that uses six sigma control charts to determine task priority. This paper focuses on a single aspect of the proposed method. [29]

proposed a cloud scheduling mechanism that works as a three stage strategy that helps to pre-create a convenient number of virtual machines with various resource attributes, saving time and resources while improving service quality. This serves to identify the optimal pairing between the task and VMs, achieve the best results of task scheduling and execution, and improve the quality of the cloud service based on the most recent scheduling data stored for tasks and their matched VMs.

VI. CONCLUSION

Cloud computing technology has become more widely used in commercial markets. The study of several job scheduling strategies has been examined in this essay. Many researchers have been researching on priority and non-priority based job scheduling approaches to maximize cloud provider's profits while maintaining client satisfaction. The incoming request needs to be scheduled in a way that maximizes the time required to allocate resources. Future research will therefore be able to create an optimal priority-based approach that combines the survey results presented here with other algorithms.

REFERENCES

1. E. H. Houssein, A. G. Gad, Y. M. Wazery, and P. N. Suganthan, "Task Scheduling in Cloud Computing based on Meta-heuristics: Review, Taxonomy, Open Challenges, and Future Trends," *Swarm Evol. Comput.*, vol. 62, no. May 2020, p. 100841, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.swevo.2021.100841.
2. F. S. Prity, M. H. Gazi, and K. M. A. Uddin, A review of task scheduling in cloud computing based on nature-inspired optimization algorithm, vol. 26, no. 5. Springer US, 2023. doi: 10.1007/s10586-023-04090-y.
3. L. Abraham, M. A. Ngadi, J. M. Sharif, and M. K. M. Sidik, "Task Scheduling in Cloud Environment-Techniques, Applications, and Tools: A Systematic Literature Review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, no. October, pp. 138252–138279, 2024, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3466529.
4. T. Saravanan and K. Ramesh, "A Bio-inspired Energy Efficient Dynamic Task Scheduling (BEDTS) scheme and classification for virtualization CDC," *J. Eng. Res.*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 387–396, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jer.2023.08.026.
5. T. M. Tawfeeg et al., "Cloud Dynamic Load Balancing and Reactive Fault Tolerance Techniques: A Systematic Literature Review (SLR)," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, no. July, pp. 71853–71873, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3188645.
6. Pradhan, S. K. Bisoy, and A. Das, "A survey on PSO based meta-heuristic scheduling mechanism in cloud computing environment," *J. King Saud Univ. - Comput. Inf. Sci.*, vol. 34, no. 8, pp. 4888–4901, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jksuci.2021.01.003.
7. M. Menaka and K. S. Sendhil Kumar, "Workflow scheduling in cloud environment – Challenges, tools, limitations & methodologies: A review," *Meas. Sensors*, vol. 24, no. July, p. 100436, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.measen.2022.100436.
8. Z. Ahmad et al., "Scientific Workflows Management and Scheduling in Cloud Computing: Taxonomy, Prospects, and Challenges," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, no. c, pp. 53491–53508, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3070785.
9. S. Singh, R. Kumar, and D. Singh, "An empirical investigation of task scheduling and VM consolidation schemes in cloud environment," *Comput. Sci. Rev.*, vol. 50, p. 100583, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.cosrev.2023.100583.
10. S. A. Murad, A. J. M. Muzahid, Z. R. M. Azmi, M. I. Hoque, and M. Kowsher, "A review on job scheduling technique in cloud computing and priority rule based intelligent framework," *J. King Saud Univ. - Comput. Inf. Sci.*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 2309–2331, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jksuci.2022.03.027.
11. R. Arunarani, D. Manjula, and V. Sugumaran, "Task scheduling techniques in cloud computing: A literature survey," *Futur. Gener. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 91, pp. 407–415, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.future.2018.09.014.
12. S. Patel and U. Bhoi, "Priority Based Job Scheduling Techniques In Cloud Computing: A Systematic Review," *Int. J. Sci. Technol. Res.*, vol. 2, no. 11, 2013, doi: 10.1.1.434.34.

13. D. Reuben Aremu and A. K. Moses, "Resource Allocation in Cloud Computing Using a Generalized Knapsack Algorithm," *LAUTECH J. Comput. Informatics*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2023, [Online]. Available: www.laujci.lautech.edu.ng
14. N. Arora and R. K. Banyal, "Hybrid scheduling algorithms in cloud computing: A review," *Int. J. Electr. Comput. Eng.*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 880–895, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i1.pp880-895.
15. R. R. & R. S. ABHINAV SRIVASTAVA, "High Compaction Coarse Grained Job Scheduling in Grid Computing," *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Eng. Inf. Technol. Res.*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 295–302, 2013, [Online]. Available: http://www.tjprc.org/view_archives.php?year=2013&jtype=2&id=14&details=archivesA. V. Karthick, E. Ramaraj, and R. G. Subramanian, "An efficient multi queue job scheduling for cloud computing," *Proc. - 2014 World Congr. Comput. Commun. Technol. WCCCT 2014*, pp. 164–166, 2014, doi: 10.1109/WCCCT.2014.8.
16. F. Alhaidari and T. Z. Balharith, "Enhanced round-robin algorithm in the cloud computing environment for optimal task scheduling," *Computers*, vol. 10, no. 5, 2021, doi: 10.3390/computers10050063.
17. G. Gupta, V. K. Kumawat, P. R. Laxmi, D. Singh, V. Jain, and R. Singh, "A simulation of priority based earliest deadline first scheduling for cloud computing system," *1st Int. Conf. Networks Soft Comput. ICNSC 2014 - Proc.*, pp. 35–39, 2014, doi: 10.1109/CNSC.2014.6906659.
18. Z. Peng, P. Pirozmand, M. Motevalli, and A. Esmaeili, "Genetic Algorithm-Based Task Scheduling in Cloud Computing Using MapReduce Framework," *Math. Probl. Eng.*, vol. 2022, 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/4290382.
19. D. A. Abdulgader, A. Yousif, and A. Ali, "A Discrete Prey–Predator Algorithm for Cloud Task Scheduling," *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 13, no. 20, pp. 1–16, 2023, doi: 10.3390/app132011447.
20. P. Pirozmand, A. A. R. Hosseinabadi, M. Farrokhzad, M. Sadeghilalimi, S. Mirkamali, and A. Slowik, "Multi-objective hybrid genetic algorithm for task scheduling problem in cloud computing," *Neural Comput. Appl.*, vol. 33, no. 19, pp. 13075–13088, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s00521-021-06002-w.
21. L. Abualigah and A. Diabat, "A novel hybrid antlion optimization algorithm for multi-objective task scheduling problems in cloud computing environments," *Cluster Comput.*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 205–223, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s10586-020-03075-5.
22. N. Sharma, Sonal, and P. Garg, "Ant colony based optimization model for QoS-based task scheduling in cloud computing environment," *Meas. Sensors*, vol. 24, no. October, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.measen.2022.100531.
23. X. Wei, "Task scheduling optimization strategy using improved ant colony optimization algorithm in cloud computing," *J. Ambient Intell. Humaniz. Comput.*, no. 0123456789, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s12652-020-02614-7.
24. C. Jianfang, C. Junjie, and Z. Qingshan, "An optimized scheduling algorithm on a cloud workflow using a discrete particle swarm," *Cybern. Inf. Technol.*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 25–39, 2014, doi: 10.2478/cait-2014-0003.
25. J. Huang, "The Workflow Task Scheduling Algorithm Based on the GA Model in the Cloud Computing Environment," *J. Softw.*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 873–880, 2014, doi: 10.4304/jsw.9.4.873-880.
26. Y. C. Lee and A. Y. Zomaya, "Energy efficient utilization of resources in cloud computing systems," *J. Supercomput.*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 268–280, 2012, doi: 10.1007/s11227-010-0421-3.
27. S. A. Murad et al., "Priority based job scheduling technique that utilizes gaps to increase the efficiency of job distribution in cloud computing," *Sustain. Comput. Informatics Syst.*, vol. 41, no. November 2023, p. 100942, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.suscom.2023.100942.
28. N. Mansouri and M. M. Javidi, "Cost-based job scheduling strategy in cloud computing environments," *Distrib. Parallel Databases*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 365–400, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s10619-019-07273-y.
29. Parsa, "RASA: A New Grid Task Scheduling Algorithm," *Int. J. Digit. Content Technol. its Appl.*, vol. 3, no. January 2009, 2009, doi: 10.4156/jdcta.vol3.issue4.10.
30. Attiya and X. Zhang, "A Simplified Particle Swarm Optimization for Job Scheduling in Cloud Computing," *Int. J. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 163, no. 9, pp. 34–41, 2017, doi: 10.5120/ijca2017913744.

31. D. Komarasamy and V. Muthuswamy, "Adaptive Deadline Based Dependent Job Scheduling algorithm in cloud computing," ICoAC 2015 - 7th Int. Conf. Adv. Comput., 2016, doi: 10.1109/ICoAC.2015.7562794.
32. M. A. Hassan, I. Kacem, S. Martin, and I. M. Osman, "Genetic algorithms for job scheduling in cloud computing," Stud. Informatics Control, vol. 24, no. 4, 2015, doi: 10.24846/v24i4y201503.
33. Li, L. Feng, and S. Fang, "An Greedy-Based Job Scheduling Algorithm in Cloud Computing," J. Softw., vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 921–925, 2014, doi: 10.4304/jsw.9.4.921-925.
34. S. Selvarani and G. S. Sadhasivam, "Improved cost-based algorithm for task scheduling in cloud computing," 2010 IEEE Int. Conf. Comput. Intell. Comput. Res. ICCIC 2010, pp. 620–624, 2010, doi: 10.1109/ICCIC.2010.5705847.
35. G. Senthilkumar, B. Suvarnamukhi, S. Lekashri, and M. M. Thaha, "Effective task scheduling based on interactive autodidactic school algorithm for cloud computing," Automatika, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 159–166, 2024, doi: 10.1080/00051144.2023.2288484.
36. S. Behzad, R. Fotohi, and M. Effatparvar, "Queue based Job Scheduling algorithm for Cloud computing," no. January 2013, 2013.
37. M. S. Sanaj and P. M. J. Prathap, "An efficient approach to the map-reduce framework and genetic algorithm based whale optimization algorithm for task scheduling in cloud computing environment," Mater. Today Proc., vol. 37, no. Part 2, pp. 3199–3208, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.09.064.
38. Y. Pachipala, K. S. Sureddy, A. B. S. Sriya Kaitepalli, N. Pagadala, S. S. Nalabothu, and M. Iniganti, "Optimizing Task Scheduling in Cloud Computing: An Enhanced Shortest Job First Algorithm," Procedia Comput. Sci., vol. 233, no. 2023, pp. 604–613, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2024.03.250.
39. Tripathy and R. R. Patra, "S i c c," vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 21–27, 2014.
40. [41]A. K. Singh, H. Singh, and M. Varsney, "Tasks Scheduling with Virtual Machines of the Deadline-Aware Priority Scheduling Model in Cloud Computing," Int. J. Intell. Syst. Appl. Eng., vol. 12, no. 8s, pp. 123–127, 2024.
41. E. Meriam and N. Tabbane, "Dynamic priority scheduling protocol based on cost in cloud computing," Proc. - 2016 Glob. Summit Comput. Inf. Technol. GSCIT 2016, pp. 15–20, 2017, doi: 10.1109/GSCIT.2016.8.
42. S. Alsubai, H. Garg, and A. Alqahtani, "A Novel Hybrid MSA-CSA Algorithm for Cloud Computing Task Scheduling Problems," Symmetry (Basel), vol. 15, no. 10, 2023, doi: 10.3390/sym15101931.
43. S. A. Murad et al., "SG-PBFS: Shortest Gap-Priority Based Fair Scheduling technique for job scheduling in cloud environment," Futur. Gener. Comput. Syst., vol. 150, pp. 232–242, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.future.2023.09.005.
44. Abu-Hashem, M. Shehab, M. K. Y. Shambour, M. S. Daoud, and L. Abualigah, "Improved Black Widow Optimization: An investigation into enhancing cloud task scheduling efficiency," Sustain. Comput. Informatics Syst., vol. 41, no. September 2023, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.suscom.2023.100949.
45. Behera and S. Sobhanayak, "Task scheduling optimization in heterogeneous cloud computing environments: A hybrid GA-GWO approach," J. Parallel Distrib. Comput., vol. 183, p. 104766, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jpdc.2023.104766.
46. S. Lipsa, R. K. Dash, N. Ivkovic, and K. Cengiz, "Task Scheduling in Cloud Computing: A Priority-Based Heuristic Approach," IEEE Access, vol. 11, no. February, pp. 27111–27126, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3255781.
47. S. Ghanbari, "Priority-Aware Job Scheduling Algorithm in Cloud Computing: a Multi-Criteria Approach," Azerbaijan J. High Perform. Comput., vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 29–38, 2019, doi: 10.32010/26166127.2019.2.1.29.38.
48. S. Ghanbari and M. Othman, "A priority based job scheduling algorithm in cloud computing," Procedia Eng., vol. 50, no. January, pp. 778–785, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.proeng.2012.10.086.
49. S. J. Patel and U. R. Bhoi, "Improved priority based job scheduling algorithm in cloud computing using iterative method," Proc. - 2014 4th Int. Conf. Adv. Comput. Commun. ICACC 2014, pp. 199–202, 2014, doi: 10.1109/ICACC.2014.55.

50. z. Saxena, R. K. Chauhan, and R. Kait, "Dynamic Fair Priority Optimization Task Scheduling Algorithm in Cloud Computing: Concepts and Implementations," *Int. J. Comput. Netw. Inf. Secur.*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 41–48, 2016, doi: 10.5815/ijcnis.2016.02.05.
51. H. Ben Alla, S. Ben Alla, A. Ezzati, and A. Touhafi, "A novel multiclass priority algorithm for task scheduling in cloud computing," vol. 77, no. 10. Springer US, 2021. doi: 10.1007/s11227-021-03741-4.
52. H. Patel and P. Richhariya, "a Multi Queue Priority Scheduling Algorithm By," no. 1, pp. 674–679.
53. S. Y. Amdani and S. R. Jadhao, "Novel hybrid cost-priority based scheduling in cloud environment," 2016 *Int. Conf. Recent Adv. Innov. Eng. ICRAIE 2016*, pp. 23–26, 2016, doi: 10.1109/ICRAIE.2016.7939552.
54. T. Karthikeyan, A. Vinothkumar, and P. Ramasamy, "Priority based scheduling in cloud computing based on task-aware technique," *J. Comput. Theor. Nanosci.*, vol. 16, no. 5–6, pp. 1942–1946, 2019, doi: 10.1166/jctn.2019.7828.
55. H. Maree, "New Optimized Priority CPU Scheduling Algorithm by using Knapsack (NOPSACK)," vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 24–31, 2020, doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31625.26722.
56. Bala and I. Chana, "Multilevel priority-based task scheduling algorithm for workflows in cloud computing environment," *Adv. Intell. Syst. Comput.*, vol. 408, pp. 685–693, 2016, doi: 10.1007/978-981-10-0129-1_71.
57. N. S. Abdelrehem, F. A. Amer, and I. A. Saroit, "Dynamic Three Stages Task Scheduling Algorithm on Cloud Computing," vol. 18, no. 6, p. 9, 2020.